

PHONEME AND LETTER RELATIONSHIP IN "DEVONU LUG'OTIT TURK".

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Abstract. This article discusses the development of Arabic linguistics, the services of Farabi, ibn Sina, Beruni, Zamakhshari, as well as the contribution of Arabic linguistics to the development of Turkology, including the relationship between sounds and letters, and their expression in "Devonu Lug'otit Turk".

Keywords: sound, phoneme, letter, Arabic linguistics, Indian linguistics, vowels, consonants

In the 10th-11th century, there was a strong mutual influence in the development of the science of the East, the Middle East and Central Asia, and this was also reflected in the development of linguistics. On the one hand, the services of Abu Nasr Farabi, Abu Ali ibn Sina, Abu Rayhan Beruni, especially Mahmud al-Zamahshari were great for the formation and development of Arabic linguistics, and on the other hand, Arabic linguistics also influenced the development of Turkology. A.Nurmanov's "History of Uzbek Linguistics" provides detailed information about this, which saves us from retraction [9. 7-26]. For example, the scientist Abu Nasr Farabi, relying on the opinion that "Innumerable contradictions replace each other", said that the roots of the contradiction of constant, stable (constant) units with changing (accident) units, which are common nowadays in the glossematic direction of structural linguistics, are also found in Farabi's works. According to him, Beruni stated in his work "Saydana" that there is a big difference in the phonological system of the Indian language and the Arabic language, and noted that there is some difficulty in rendering Indian words in Arabic. added four (*p, ch, j, g*) letters. Abu Ali ibn Sina's work "Instrument" is devoted to general phonetics issues, and at the same time, it is pure synchronous phonetics in which the physiological and acoustic properties of sounds are studied without considering the issue of phonetic changes [9.21].

"Al Mufassal" ("Comprehensive Book on Grammar") by our great ancestor Mahmud al-Zamahshari, who created more than 50 works on Arabic grammar, lexicology, literature, science of aruz, geography, tafsir, hadith and fiqh, is a great work in the study of the use of the Arabic language. as a guide has long been famous both in the East and in the West [12. 657-658].

The formation and development of Arabic linguistics and the creation of its theoretical foundations were strongly influenced by Indian and Greek linguistics, especially by Indian linguistics, which distinguished between sounds and phonemes [8.24, 3.9].

period at the request of according to his works Arabic in the language wrote of our ancestors creative in the activity this of the tongue effect that it was clearly _ That's why for and " in Turkology " of our scientists phonetics and to phonology about initial views Arabic philology and Arabic linguistics under the influence of surface came to say it is possible , " he said in his thoughts soul there is [5.63]. This reasoning Mahmud To Koshgari too applies . To

the scientist that's it times lexicology , lexicography with together phonetics issue too serious teachable Baghdad linguistics of the school lessons hand came _ So Mahmoud _ _ Koshgari turkish of languages to himself special phonetic features open in giving not only Arabic Linguistics , perhaps herk and indian of linguistics achievements relied upon too natural one case being comes out

That's right , Mahmoud Koshgari « Devonu dictionary in the work "Turk " . sounds system to research special chap did not separate . But dictionary of units explanation to give in the process speech sounds on the surface did analyses him own of the era big phonetic scientist that let us say full basis be takes _ A scientist to sounds circle the road is on the road of notes in itself too that's it period of the language phonetic features much wide commented .

Mahmoud Koshgari's phonetic their views Uzbek in the language first there is analysis did scientist S. _ Mutallibov being is considered To his " Devon " . included "XI century great linguist scientist Mahmoud Koshgari » named in the article this of views brief statement given

From " Devon " . It is understood that Mahmoud Koshgari each one the sound special observed , his each one deep learned and explained . Speech of sounds combinatorial in use position , physiological and acoustic cases sure set came out Turkish languages sound pronunciation circle circumstances analysis so , own period linguistics to phonetics about important the rules with enriched _

Including sound _ and letters attitude the first being determined scientist vowels system , in them breadth and narrowness , longness and of brevity turkish tribes to the language special aspects and application principles around explained . Consonant in sounds sonority and slang , their row come get and come sonority , sonority feature like issues too reliable way commented .

Mahmoud _ Koshgari of the tongue the most small element calculated sounds and their in writing begili - letters about , speech of sounds breadth and narrowness , longness and shortness , hardness and softness features about , resounding and detonation , in words sound down stay , assimilation like phonetic processes about too wide stopped and own thoughts turkish from languages given many original examples through explaining gave " _ writes H. _ Berdyarov [2.15]. That's it way scientist present in linguistics phoneme the term with maintained phonological unity , sound type scientific justification with together , his practical importance too showing gave _ Speech of sounds the amount three demand - pronunciation , hearing and meaning difference on demand answer to give point of view in terms of learned and of them the most the main thing meaning differentiate feature the fact that about to the conclusion came _

That's why for Orientalist P. _ K. _ Jose Mahmoud Koshgari and his " Devon " i about the following when writing completely right was : "... Brave to say maybe recently (XIX century at the end of) in Russia and in the east studied turkish languages phonetics and etymology main laws as early as the 11th century Mahmoud by determined was _ of Mahmoud this checks that's it until wide and deep , even such the work is in the 19th century when written too , to him glory - honor would be Mahmoud " Devon " of Koshgari like work science in the world next in centuries too created not _ His work bamisoli « Turkish dictionary " is " [6. 75-94, 13.15].

This in the department speech sounds , in particular , phoneme and to the letter about comments analysis will be done .

the X-XI centuries of the world many countries , including Ort _ in Asia too in consumption has been Arabic writing turkish nations in his life certain role that he played that's right , of course . But his Arabic didn't happen nations by in consumption of being difficulties too the eye closed it won't be . This difficulties and from him come coming out problems linguistic in studies more sure manifestation it happened This direction observations Arabic writing and turkish of nations sound pronunciation between to inconsistencies certainties input requirement enough was _ Mahmoud Koshgari too initially mother that's it to the problem face came _ Of this because of it E. _ Umarov Arabic in the language three short **fatha - a , kasra - i , zamma - u** and three long (**alif - a ; vov - u ; arc - i** :) – total six vowel availability , Turkish in languages while they are from 9 to 16 the fact that with explains [11. 74]. That's it regardless , " Mahmud Koshgari in Turkology the first times sounds and letters between relationship sure showed and in writing is available letters oral conversation in his speech of sounds all of them express that he can't show with together , Turkish pronunciation Arabic in his writing sure to express for again seven letter necessity scientific respectively proof by doing gave » [2. 15]. There that's it in a sense Mahmoud Koshgari by first there is Arabic writing and turkish in languages sounds relationship of the issue put and positive solution to be done very big scientific and educational important have was _

Mahmoud Koshgari phoneme with of the letter attitude characters it is Turkish of words in the structure applied letters about » stopping , their basically here this l t sh r j b s n m d k y Q zw kh f 18 of them letter that said and them the following six to the word placing showed : **بدر . شتيا . nzq . smj_ lf. k khw 1**[DLT . I,47].

Mahmoud Koshgari this of letters in Arabic peer types existence to emphasize with together , Turkish in languages again addition phonemes existence , Turkish words without them not to be used note did _ The same at the time of their Arabic in his writing special letter with not expressed from flying except that _ of sounds in pronunciation to himself special aspects showed and their literally expression marked : « In Arabic this of letters peer Sira **eh b t th** is like This main from the letters another only in pronunciation (in writing not) expressible again seven letter Turkish _ _ words this without letters is not used . These are hard pronunciation to be done **b (p)** letter , Arabic **j (j)** The letter is Arabic *silent* (this in the dictionary , ie in turkish less applied) , **j (z)** with **III (III)** between pronunciation to be done **з (j)** letter _ Arabic **(f)** _ letter , dotted **r (r ')** letter , **q (q)** with **k (k)** letters between pronunciation to be done soft **k = □ (g)** , enough good luck with **r (r ')** between and **Q** with **n** between pronunciation are the letters to be made (**ñ**) » [DLT . I,48] [7. 27-28].

T. _ A. _ Borovkova this is 18 arabic of the letter Uighur alphabet with suitable to come , next seven letter while Uighur in the alphabet lack of for that it was used says _ Also this _ letters between strong explosive **p (p)** _ expressive p b ā' sulba (hard , strong) and articulation f with b between has been c f ā' raqiqa (soft , weak , weak) letters existence note this is it of the letter in use Mahmoud Koshgari of sound weakness mean held and he slippery lip - tooth sound **c** to right comes , says [4. 24].

Mahmoud Koshgari phonemes and their in writing expression level one different that it is not , that is phoneme with letter between relationship always too suitable not coming about important thoughts statement did [10. 35, 1., 7.27-28]. For example , A , w letters vowel to express with together , compound in the form of " thick - thin " symbol with difference doer and word the meaning to differentiate service who does one how many phoneme express note

reached _ For example , in the word **ot** (**grass**) . vowel thick pronunciation fire _ _ _ _ _
meaning , thin (**ö** in the style of) pronunciation if done , *on the wall and on the board hole* ,
more thinner pronunciation if possible , *go bag* the meaning means will fly It seems that their
each one separately lexeme and of lexemes meaning the difference surface in bringing
phoneme important place holds :» ° üt' **horse - grass , fire** ; ° تيساغير كيماس ° üt' **ot tēcä a g ' ë z kÿj**
m äc - *grass said with mouth do not burn* ; ° üt'öt - [w letter thin (**ö** in the style of)
pronunciation is done] *on the wall and on the board has been hole* _ ° üt' **ö t** (w letter from
above too thinner pronunciation is done) – *bitterness , grass [ö] bag* » [DLT . I,78-79].

Har one of the people speech sounds surface bringer articulation to himself special and
this aspect , first next , phonetic in processes manifestation will be That's why for different in
the language some sounds pronunciation in doing difficulties to the body will come There
that's it in a sense Mahmoud Koshgari's the following words attention owner : " This is letters
(quoted seven sound expression mean eclipsed - MM) pronunciation in doing from the Turks
others they suffer . This letters like those (above) letters is written on top point put will be
separated » [DLT . I,48].

In " Devon " . Arabic in the inscription graphemes with turkish phonemes between
imbalance big that it was therefore this writing turkish languages phonetic (phonological)
system sure and right express can't too shown . This is it in writing some letters only Arabic to
the language special has been phonemes only from expressing come out , the following note
added : " Someone tribe in the language too **th** letter there is no Dog from the letters to be **ţ z**
□□ letters too turkish in languages there is no Also , the throat from the sounds to be **h** °
letters too turkish in languages there is no » [DLT . I,48].

A scientist of your opinion proof for **ky** ° **k**° = **ky** ° **ÿkk** the word **h**° **Yes** those who say
very lack , ° **ky** ° the word **k** with pronunciation to do pinch that , kanjaks fire wood yes **yes**,
the eye the pain ° **abäh** they say , however this words language feature suitable that it is not
note is enough

Mahmoud Koshgari in his view sometimes word in the joint to stop , pause , that is
foundation in the situation of the word to the end **h** phoneme by joining coming too possible :
falcon the bird in calling **tah-tah** , kulinni in calling **q̣ṛḥ q̣ṛḥ beautiful** is called
However in the Turks **h (h)** with applied one too word no _ Indian of the language under the
influence of Khotan people in the language some in words this phoneme meeting stay can _ A
scientist **h** kanjaks in the language to meet too his turkish that it is not tie explains .

Mahmoud Koshgari this of letters all of them collected their _ format - letter harvest
does and this system based on some of phonemes pronunciation with spelling between
imbalances existence Arabic language measure based on comments : " This the letter in
writing , in pronunciation place to the absence despite , in writing one different characters is
increased . For example , increase in place **w** (vov) , vowel in place **y** (arc) , fatha in place **1** (**alif**)
characters to write is a rule . In Arabic **b** □ **ح** □ words another words with by joining
when it comes in pronunciation sure imperceptible **eh w y** letters the addition of that's it
example is [DLT . I,49-50].

Also Arabic _ in graphics is available has been from difficulties come out , some
phonemes and their shaped relationship about so writes : " If **th** the letter to write need if so ,
Turkish **d (z)** in the picture written on it point is placed . **d** too **d** in the form of written on it
point is placed . **s** letter too **s** in the form of written on it point is placed . **h** ° **h** letters turkish
kh in the form of Some are written sign with will be separated » [DLT . I,48]. The author this

phonemes to Arabic characteristic of this letters turkish if written , in the form similarity if saved also , period and characters with the difference , all Turk in the cities - from Kashkar Really all hawks and of the sultans books , records ancient of times that's it until the day this writing with that it is finished note is enough

It is understood that Mahmoud Koshgari " Devon " . in writing turkish phonemes and Arabic graphics between inconsistencies to be regardless , Turkish nations pronunciation possible until suitable coming , one until comfortable from spelling used and that's it road with from this a thousand year previous turkish linguistic of inheritance trouble without seeing until us reached to come provided

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